

THE CONCEPT OF GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE AS A GOAL OF FORMATION IN A LANGUAGE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: This article examines the concept of educational competence, the component structure of foreign language communicative competence, and the content of teaching the grammatical aspect of speech. The aim is to determine the role and place of grammatical competence within foreign language communicative competence and to provide its definition.

Keywords: educational competence, foreign language grammatical competence, content of teaching the grammatical aspect of speech, grammatical competence.

1 Introduction.

According to the educational standard of higher professional education in Uzbekistan, future foreign language teachers must acquire a range of general cultural, general professional, and professional competencies, which are formed within the subjects of the basic part of the general professional cycle [1, pp. 5-8]. They must also master special competencies, which are developed through the study of language disciplines included in the variable part of the professional cycle.

We are particularly interested in the special competencies of future foreign language teachers, which, according to the Core Educational Program, include:

Proficiency in the skills of perceiving, understanding, and conducting a multifaceted analysis of spoken and written discourse in the target foreign language.

The ability to use linguistic means to achieve communicative goals in specific communication situations in the target foreign language.

The ability to develop oral and written communication strategies in the target foreign language in accordance with the sociocultural characteristics of the studied language [2, p. 8].

2 Technology of Material Acquisition and Research Method

All these components are part of foreign language communicative competence (FLCC), which is the goal of foreign language education in linguistic universities. Before discussing this concept, let us examine the place of FLCC within the structure of educational competencies as defined by A. V. Khutorskoy.

According to Khutorskoy, "educational competence is a set of semantic orientations, knowledge, skills, abilities, and practical experience of a student in relation to a specific set of real-world objects, necessary for carrying out personally and socially significant productive activities" [3]. All these components form the foundation of students' ability to perform personally and socially significant productive activities (in our case, foreign language speech activity). This is the understanding of educational competence that we will adopt in this study.

The aforementioned author proposes a three-level hierarchy of competencies:

Key competencies – related to the general content of education.

General subject competencies – related to a specific range of academic subjects and educational fields.

Subject-specific competencies – more specialized than the previous two levels, with concrete descriptions and the potential to be developed within academic subjects.

3 Experimental Results and Their Discussion

The key educational competencies include value-semantic, general cultural, learning and cognitive, informational, communicative, socio-labor, and personal self-improvement competencies. From this list, it is evident that communicative competence, on the one hand, is one of the key educational competencies. On the other hand, according to the modern concept of foreign language education, it is also a priority goal of foreign language instruction, thus belonging to the category of subject-specific competencies.

In the works of Russian and foreign scholars (I. L. Bim, M. N. Vyatutnev, N. D. Galskova, R. K. Minyar-Beloruhev, A. N. Shchukin, S. Brumfit), FLCC is interpreted in various ways. Some define it as "the ability to use the linguistic system appropriately and effectively" [4]. Others describe FLCC as "the ability to implement linguistic competence in different speech communication contexts, taking into account social norms of behavior and the communicative appropriateness of utterances" [5, p. 43].

The term "communicative competence" was introduced into Russian linguistic didactics by M. N. Vyatutnev, who proposed understanding communicative competence as "the selection and implementation of speech behavior programs depending on a person's ability to navigate a particular communicative environment; the ability to classify situations based on topic, objectives, and communicative settings that arise before and during conversations in the process of mutual adaptation" [6, p. 45].

Communicative competence is also understood as "the ability to use the target language to carry out speech activities in accordance with communication goals and situations within a given field of activity" [7, p. 140]. Similarly, N. D. Galskova defines FLCC as "a person's ability to understand and generate foreign language utterances in various socially determined situations, considering the linguistic and social rules followed by native speakers" [8, p. 19].

According to I. L. Bim, FLCC is the ability and actual readiness to engage in foreign language communication with native speakers, as well as to introduce students to the culture of the target language country, enhance their understanding of their own country's culture, and represent it in communication [9, p. 159].

For our research, all these definitions highlight the critical aspect that FLCC is the ability and real readiness of students to engage in foreign language communication with native speakers in various socially determined situations, considering linguistic and social norms.

Next, we will examine the component structure of FLCC to determine the role of grammatical competence within it. As is well known, FLCC consists of several sub-competencies, whose number and content vary across different sources. For example, the structure of this competence in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages [10, p. 108] includes linguistic, sociolinguistic, and pragmatic competencies.

M. Canale and M. Swain [11] identify grammatical (sometimes called linguistic), discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies. N. I. Gez describes verbal-cognitive, linguistic, verbal-communicative, and metacommunicative competencies as components of FLCC [12, p. 18].

R. P. Milrud and I. R. Maksimova propose the following classification of sub-competencies: linguistic, pragmatic, cognitive, and informational [13, pp. 13-15]. Based on these classifications, it can be concluded that linguistic (or grammatical) competence is one of the fundamental sub-competencies necessary for the functioning of FLCC in university graduates, along with sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competencies. Therefore, its development is given significant attention in the training of future foreign language teachers, particularly in the first year of study.

This raises the question: what exactly is grammatical competence, and what role does it play within FLCC? According to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, grammatical competence is the knowledge of a language's grammatical means and the ability to use them. However, in our view, this definition does not fully capture all aspects of educational competence, as it does not address the ability to perform socially significant productive activities.

M. Canale and M. Swain define grammatical competence as encompassing knowledge of lexical units and rules of morphology, syntax, sentence semantics, and phonology [11]. This definition focuses on knowledge of various rules, which alone, without the accompanying skills and abilities, cannot ensure

learners' ability to engage in foreign language speech activities. Furthermore, knowledge of lexical units is not the key aspect of grammatical competence.

N. I. Gez defines linguistic competence as the ability to comprehend and produce an unlimited number of grammatically correct sentences based on acquired linguistic knowledge and the rules of their combination [12, p. 18]. This definition, firstly, does not distinguish between lexical and grammatical skills, and secondly, it presents this ability as "detached" from its sphere of application, namely, foreign language speech activity, which, according to A. V. Khutorsky, should be personally and socially significant.

R. P. Milrud and I. R. Maksimova define linguistic subcompetence as the readiness to use a foreign language as a tool for speech and cognitive activity [13, pp. 13-15], but they overlook key concepts such as knowledge, skills, abilities, and experience in foreign language speech activity, which, in our view, are essential for a complete understanding of competence.

As we can see, all the above definitions of grammatical competence do not fully reflect the fundamental definition of educational competence mentioned earlier. Additionally, they interpret its structure and content differently. To provide a more precise and comprehensive definition of grammatical competence, we will examine what students need to master in the process of learning the grammatical aspect of foreign language speech activity, in other words, what the content of learning the grammatical aspect of speech entails.

According to A. N. Shamov [14, p. 90], the content of learning the grammatical aspect of speech "includes everything that contributes to the development of grammatical skills." The author identifies three components in the content of learning the grammatical aspect of foreign language speech: linguistic, psychological, and methodological. Let us consider the content of learning the grammatical aspect of foreign language speech within each of these components.

The linguistic component includes, firstly, the grammatical minimum, which represents a specific set of grammatical phenomena (grammatical forms, structures, rules for word modification, and their combination into sentences) necessary for the correct formulation of speech, both morphologically and syntactically. Secondly, it also includes grammatical rules, which contain "a specific list of differential features of grammatical phenomena that characterize their properties and sequence of realization in oral and written communication." In other words, grammatical rules provide information on the formal features of a grammatical phenomenon, its meaning (semantic characteristics), function in the speech context, and peculiarities of its usage [8, p. 313].

4 Conclusion

All parts of the linguistic component constitute grammatical knowledge, which enables foreign language learners to gain a deeper understanding of grammatical phenomena and consciously apply this knowledge when acquiring grammatical material and producing speech utterances.

Based on the definition of educational competence mentioned earlier and considering the content of learning the grammatical aspect of speech, we propose defining grammatical competence as students' ability and readiness to comprehend and produce grammatically correct utterances for personally significant foreign language speech activity in various socially determined situations. It is founded on grammatical knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as the methods of working with them, which students must master as subjects of foreign language communication and learning activities. We will use this understanding of the phenomenon as one of the special subcompetencies of ICC, which is given significant attention in teaching first-year language students at our university.

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